

Letter from the Editor

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Technician Education Community,

On behalf of myself, the J ATE Editorial Board, and our staff, I am excited to present the Journal of Advanced Technological Education (J ATE) Volume 2, Issue 1. J ATE is the peer-reviewed journal for community and technical colleges involved in technician education. J ATE is cross-discipline and covers all technologies under the National Science Foundation (NSF) Advanced Technological Education (ATE) Program. J ATE is open access: free to submit and free to read. All of our articles are released under a creative commons license.

We welcome your article in the next issue of J ATE. Here at J ATE, we strive not only to maintain high standards of quality and transparency in our peer-review process, but also to be welcoming, inviting, and helpful to new authors. Our goal is to guide your manuscript through the publication process and to help you produce your best work possible.

This is J ATE's second full year, and we have seen remarkable growth. This issue contains five invited letters, and eleven full articles. Compared to our first issue, this is double the number of articles and about double the number of pages! *J ATE is growing.*

The theme of this issue is *Industry Engagement*.

Industry engagement is essential for successful community and technical college technician programs and happens with academic technician programs in a variety of ways. For example, industry regularly hires students and its representatives serve on advisory boards. Industry employees often work as part-time instructors, provide guest lectures, facilitate mock interviews, and interact on many different levels with students, faculty, and staff. This issue of J ATE highlights the work of several industry-academic collaborations.

The next J ATE issue will focus on undergraduate research at community and technical colleges. The submission deadline is **May 31, 2023**. [Submit your article](#) to J ATE and become a published author.

We invite you to join our community. Besides writing and reading J ATE, you can participate in several ways:

- Join our monthly Readers Group, Writers Group, or Reviewers Group

- Participate in our Professional Development Workshop [Sept. 12 – 14, 2023](#)
- Serve as a J ATE Reviewer
- Visit us at the [HI-TEC Conference](#) and NSF [ATE PI Conference](#)

If you have an article idea, don't hesitate to get in touch with me or any of the other J ATE Editors. We'd love to chat with you about your ideas and how to turn your great research into a published paper.

In Teaching and Learning,
Peter D. Kazarinoff
Editor-in-Chief